

WAYS TO INCREASE THE POPULARITY OF RETAIL SERVICES IN BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article explores the scientific and theoretical foundations of retail banking services, studies the practice of their development in developed foreign practice. Also, based on the importance of information technology in the development of retail services, the possibilities of their widespread use were considered.

Keywords: retail banking, remote banking services, deposit, internet banking, mobile banking, client bank, online banking.

The “Strategy of Action for Five Priority Areas of Development of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021” also states that “to reform the banking system, deepen capitalization and increase the stability of the deposit base of banks, strengthen their financial stability and reliability.” promising investment projects and small businesses have been identified and the task of further expanding lending to business entities has been identified.”

In fact, the development of the market for commercial banking services not only allows capital to be channeled into the national economy, but also ensures that the population is informed, speeds up payments and creates a number of other conveniences and opportunities. Based on this, we have to study the experience of foreign countries in the field of retail banking services and introduce the positive aspects of this experience, based on the internal situation in the banking system of Uzbekistan.

Banks are funding or acquiring fintech startups to develop and maintain their position as “digital” banks specializing in retail services. This situation, observed

all over the world, will undoubtedly affect the banks of our country. In a survey and study conducted by Efma and Infosys Finacle, banks (74%) said they increased investment in innovation projects in 2016-17 compared to previous years. 69% of banks said that they have become innovative banks, and 25% of banks consider their innovative activities to be at a high level. More than 40% of banks work with startups and 30% of banks said they have invested in startups [8].

Innovation and digital transformation go hand in hand, and 20% of responding banks have outsourced their retail services to dedicated digital banking. 85% of these banks offer new services and products, and 81% conduct banking transactions using new systems. As a foundation for innovation and digital transformation, 78% of banks strive to offer customers high-quality services and products, 74% of banks strive to implement new systems, and 68% strive to effectively use mobile and social technologies.

The threat posed by fintech and technology companies was estimated at 47% in 2016 and 48% in 2017. Fintech and technology companies are becoming a worthy competitor to banks due to their high adaptability and ability to quickly adapt and innovate. Therefore, banks' collaboration with Fintech startups and technology companies can create opportunities for them to respond to customer and market demands in the future. This situation has a significant impact mainly on developed countries (USA, EU, Brazil, China, South Africa, Australia and similar countries), and banks in these countries have a generally positive attitude towards technological changes and innovative projects, but in banks in developing countries these changes have not received enough attention.

The main competitors of banks in the field of retail services are mobile application payment systems, and 86% of banks in the world say that this threat is very serious and that banks have only two options, the first is to cooperate with Fintech startups and technology companies. and second, fintech and technology

companies are insisting that banks develop products and services. Banks in developed countries are constantly monitoring fintechs. Ralf Hamers, head of ING Group (Netherlands), said that ING Group always studies market demand and supply and cooperates with 45 fintech companies in the field of payment management, system development, mobilization and lending.

To achieve the strategic goal of improving the market for retail banking services in Uzbekistan, banking activities should develop in the following areas:

- standardization and automation of the process of providing retail banking services.

- development of a strategy for the implementation of modern sales, including the development and optimization of the branch system.

- expanding the range of retail banking services and improving their quality.

We believe that solving these problems will further improve the market for retail banking services and satisfy the needs of bank clients.

As a result of analyzing the prospects for the development of remote banking services in Uzbekistan, the following proposals and recommendations were developed:

1. Each commercial bank must develop its own strategic program for the development of remote banking services in commercial banks and the development of a system of remote customer service. As part of this program, it will be necessary to develop a roadmap for the phased transfer of all types of services to remote and online mode. The source of funding, the timing of the implementation of the tasks defined in this roadmap, and the department responsible for the implementation and the launch period of the project should be indicated.

2. Currently, the types of services provided by commercial banks remotely include utility and other payments, card-to-card money transfers, online conversion, online deposit services, as well as retail lending services in some

banks. their type in the next step. In particular, these include sending and receiving funds abroad through integration with international money transfers, including the virtual card issuance service.

3. It is natural that the development of remote banking services will reveal the need for customer identification. Taking this into account, it would be advisable to create opportunities to integrate all mobile banking services from the Ministry of Internal Affairs database if it is necessary to identify a customer service employee.

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